

METHODS OF USING THE "PROFESSIONAL" METHOD IN TEACHING STUDENTS TO DRAW PORTRAITS IN PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Annotation: *The article is devoted to one of the urgent problems of professional training of future teachers in the classroom for drawing, making a portrait using the cutting method. It discusses the issues of the anatomical and linear constructive structure of the human head, provides examples of how to correctly depict a portrait, and analyzes the structure of the human head.*

Key words: *artist-teacher, visual arts, painting, composition, methodology, abilities, artistic image, creativity, perception*

It is known that the depiction of a human portrait in drawing lessons is one of the most difficult and interesting tasks of pedagogy in higher education. Before making a pencil drawing of a human portrait, future artists and teachers must know its anatomical structure, the main parts and parts of the head, their interconnectedness. In this case, the use of the method of classical craftsmen "Cutting" helps to accurately describe both the general and the components of the head on paper. This method allows students to focus on the main content of the larger form, rather than on the outer parts (eyebrows, eyelashes, etc.). This task may not seem difficult to understand, but it is more difficult for a student to describe it in practice. To alleviate this problem, French artists of the last century pointed out that the Dupuis brothers needed to use "sharp" shapes to teach them to draw.

When we analyze the shape of the head, we see that, in general, its skull has certain patterns of formation.

In the description it is necessary to emphasize the general character of the head shape and to clarify the direction of the individual surfaces in width, to observe the correct formation. The main purpose of showing the shape in the image is to highlight the shape of the head, the most characteristic places. The artist, who will work on the method of expressing a large form, is forced to give up the small parts of the structure of the form, to focus only on the larger parts of the volume, to see the wholeness, the generality.

In order to teach how to see unity, it is necessary to know what elements this unity consists of, and how these parts and components fit together. Correct description of the head requires the student to observe nature and work methodically in the description. Acquiring a method of analyzing and expressing a large form in an image improves the writer's ability to anticipate the results of drawing, that is, to imagine in advance what the image he draws will look like in the end.

Such training should be based on analytical methods. When an artist depicts the shape of the head, he must be able to see how the volume is formed from individual surfaces, how the constructive basis of the shape is formed. The artist has to observe the form and subdue the generalized form of the model to the plastic expression by hand movements in the pen.

When describing the size of the head, it is important to keep in mind that there are two main parts to the head. These are the spherical shape of the skull and the occipital bone. The artist should take into account the general structure of the skull and connect the lower part of the jaw with the main parts of the skull.

Continuing the analysis of the head form and its components, it is necessary to emphasize a number of other laws related to the exaggeration of the major form. For example, the nose is based on a prism. For an artist who knows this law of the shape of the nose, it is no longer difficult to describe it on paper. It is more difficult to give a perspective view of the shape of the nose in the picture. Creating a perspective view of a prism is not a problem even for a novice artist.

1 picture. *Nose's perspective is based on geometric shapes*

In the description of the "cut" head,

working on other parts and fragments based on geometric shapes, helps the student to spatially imagine the whole shape. In addition, the shape and surface the use of this method of analysis of expression helps the artist to solve the form in different ways.

2 pictures. *A pencil drawing depicting the*

shape of an eye in two cases

The artist, who marks the prism of the nose bounded by four surfaces on a piece of paper, immediately distinguishes the color symbols - light, shadow, half-shadows, and then determines the character of the nose and begins to model the shape of small parts. The shape of the eye is the same as the shape of a ball, and it is no coincidence that it is called "eyeball" in special literature. However, when drawing the head, it should be taken into account that the eyeball (also called "eyeball" in Uzbek dialects) is visible only one-third of the eyeball. In addition, the eyelids begin to moderately on the eyelids and eyelids, and the shape should be slower. 2 pictures.

It should be noted that in the early stages of depicting the head, when using the method of "cutting", it is not necessary to exaggerate and indulge in the creation of "cubism". This can be seen in some painters. When working on a hierarchical task, the hierarchy of shaping does not occupy a significant place, it only helps the artist.

Using the "cut" method, the artist develops the ability to see the most important thing in the description, to logically perceive what is seen, and to clearly imagine this plastic image. If the artist is unable to comprehend and imagine the features of the main form, and is limited only by his emotions, then he is forced to passively copy the nature, to imitate the appearance in such a way. As long as the student does not work with the figurative imagination, he cannot come close to generalization, or from the point of view of perception, such an image is a generalized image of nature. Well-known psychologists, as a result of research in the fine arts, have come to the conclusion that when they show the process of imagining, they assume that imagining this or that object is formed in the process of perceiving it many times. Thus, the effectiveness and expediency of the method of "professional work" in the acquisition of the art of drawing has been proven not only in artistic practice, but also in the knowledge of psychology and pedagogy.

The "cutting" method not only teaches the artist the stylistic stages of painting, but also helps him to master the language of realistic art. When a student determines the orientation of a surface in width and tries to give it the correct image, he learns to convey the image of the object by means of description and masters the laws of description.

In most cases, it is difficult for the student to use the method of analysis and expression in the portrait. It describes the general appearance of the "large form" structure, usually limited to the linear constructive appearance of the head, and goes on to describe the parts of the form without studying

the nature and size of the form. Then, without revealing the basis of the form, he begins to draw by copying the details of the shape of the nose, eyes, lips.

That is why, as mentioned above, it is necessary to do special exercises in order to master the method of expressing a large form by the method of "cutting".

You can start such exercises by placing a plaster head in front of you. To do this, describe the generalized shape of the head in geometric shapes as a whole, and then set the task of drawing the large shapes of the main details, not the nose, but the prism, and therefore all in a generalized form. At the same time, it is necessary to carefully observe the proportional relationship between the parts and the whole, noting the spherical shape of the prism of the nose. Figures 1 and 2 above illustrate such exercises. Let the student understand that the purpose of such exercises is not to express the shape of the head, but to be a stage of service, a beginning, which is creatively connected with the process of drawing. Therefore, the simplified expression of "cut head" made of gypsum models, along with "Bolvanka", it is necessary to draw live head drawings in parallel. If the artist draws his self-portrait in the mirror, this method is better mastered. Instead of copying the small parts that attract his attention, he focuses only on drawing the bulk of the volume, which requires a great will and a sense of confidence to perform the assigned task.

2nd year student J. Antoine Goodon's line drawing based on the masterpiece "Ekroshe"

In order for the "cut" method not to become the norm, but also to be considered as a short step in the description, it is necessary to create a more realistic picture. In order to master the general process of painting, it is necessary to continue painting from scratch. Since these tasks are considered as exercises, it takes a maximum of 3-4 hours to complete such a task.

Exercises for drawing a pencil in the form of "cut head" are also based on the methodological consistency in describing all learning tasks. They include:

1. Follow the cross-sectional model from different points, make pencil

drawings and choose the most suitable place, and place the natural composition correctly on paper.

2. Construction of a linear structure from the point of plunder, comparing nature to geometric shapes.

3. Correctly determine the relationship of the shapes found on the basis of a linear construct, to give the initial light shades.

4. Identify light-shadow relationships. Marking personal, falling, shadow, semi-shadow and photo lights, achieving a realistic appearance of the form in space, as well as completing the task.

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